

Waves of Happiness-A Positive Revolution

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Abstract-

The present Article “Waves of Happiness- A Positive Revolution” is a research on application of Happiness Curriculum in Schools of D.O.E. (Directorate of Education), Delhi. The curriculum has brought a positive revolution not only in the behavioral issues of the school going children but in the adults as well .

As we know that happiness is the ultimate goal of every individual. Everyone wants to lead a stress free and happy life but nobody knows How? To reduce that pressure, overcoming all the hurdles and still remain calm and composed is a big challenge. The article focuses on how happiness curriculum is the route to keep the mind calm and compose in all the walks of life.

Students across the schools of Delhi have been practicing mindfulness and learning compassion, love and affection through stories, exercises and expression. The process has changed the total behavior of the students and teachers. They have got elevated mentally, emotionally physically and socially paving the way to their success.

Thus the main objective of present article is to highlight the change in the behavior of the students thereby creating good citizens and humans above all.

Key words: Resilient, Optimism, Receptive, Rumination, Foster, Holistic, Stress, Anxiety, Contentment.

“Happiness is a journey, not a destination. Enjoy the ride.”

Happiness is the final journey of life. It is the ultimate goal of every individual. It is the feeling of contentment and joy that comes from within. It is the feeling of satisfaction and fulfillment that comes from achieving one’s goals and dreams. It is the feeling of being at peace with oneself and the world around us.

School life is a time is very stressful for children as they have to deal with a variety of pressures. In our school through happiness curriculum students are learning compassion, to be patient, understanding, to be grateful for the good things in their lives. They are also learning to be

grateful for the blessings they have received. It makes them humble and enables them to be resilient and to keep going even when things get tough with optimism. It is helping them to manage their emotions and reactions in a better way overcoming the pangs of stress and anxiety.

Many of our children shared their experiences after attending happiness classes in the school. Sakshi Yadav of 8-A shared that she never used to take advice from anyone but now she is receptive to all suggestions and never feels irritated. This has improved her performance in studies she is happy

and satisfied now.

Tammana of class 7-A also feels good when she empathizes with her grandparents, spends time with them and helps them in daily routine activities.

When our mind is calm, peaceful and happy we start appreciating beauty opening all doors of our mind to all that which lies beyond our inner fortress such as rumination, reflection, certainty and expectation. It helps the students to become aware of the values and goals which in turn guide them to take decisions in life. The mindset takes the students to the stream where every action is effortless and life becomes a miracle, full of possibilities. It also takes them to a point where the mind looks neither forward nor backward.

Regular mindful exercises help the children in fostering a sense of community where they feel accepted regardless of differences. These activities strengthen social ties. Overall introducing mindfulness in schools seems like a powerful tool for promoting holistic wellbeing amongst children and young people.

Yuvika of 8- A learnt from one of the happiness stories that we must amend ourselves first. As she learnt from the story of pandit who left eating sweets first himself before directing the boy. Mindfulness in happiness classes sets the mind of the students by intensifying the presence to the moment, stilling them to absorb it instead of escaping it and trying to alter it through thought reactions. Their mindset creates awareness about the surroundings and environment.

Khushi Shukla of 8-A admitted that she used to watch tv while eating but now she has learnt mindful eating and is able to concentrate in studies and sports much better than earlier.

Diya of 7-B is doing good in studies and she feels immensely happy when her work is praised, her drawings are displayed in the class. She is selected in dance and singing competitions and she scores 20/20 in her class test.

Afsha Khan of 6-A she used to feel heaviness in her shoulders which has gradually subsided after mindful breathing and other activities.

Sakeena bright student of 8-A used to lack confidence and gets nervous easily before others such as during assembly etc. But now she feels bold and confident and can face the public. She happily participates in various activities conducted at school and zonal level.

Our Happiness teachers are confronting such live examples frequently.

We teachers have witnessed after keeping a close watch on the students that mindfulness has lowered their aggression, stress and anxiety and they have improved in their academics and working potential.

Aisha - a student of class 8- A was a very shorttempered and aggressive child. She herself admits and accepts that she used to fight with her classmates and family members and used to create fuss over trifling issues. She remains disturbed and academic performance was going down gradually. But mindfulness brought a drastic change in her behavior and temperament. She is now a very positive, cool, calm and cooperative student. She remains happy

And smiling and cooperates with other children. Her performance in studies is also improving.

Kajal of 6-A was a child who was noticed to be quiet, and depressed as she was under medication of severe headache.

Mindfulness breathing in the class was very effective for her as her headache vanished within few days. At present she is not taking any medicine, her grades have got improved and she is now a happy and cheerful child excelling in every school activities.

Students feel good about themselves this promotes positivity in them.

Parents complaining of eating disorder of their children are now happy to share that the whole family practices mindfulness every day and enjoy their meal together. Teaching mindfulness helps them to develop positive coping strategies for dealing with stressors such as class tests and bullying by other children. It leads to better academic performance as students are able to focus on their studies rather than getting distracted by negative thoughts and emotions. It also improves relationship between teachers and students

These activities have been linked with increasing physical activities instead of focusing solely on desk work. Application of happiness curriculum in schools has brought a positive revolution in the behavioral issues of the children. It is not merely sitting in silence which is difficult for the children but it is something which can be incorporated into their breathing, eating, walking, studying and thinking.

Concluding we can say that Happiness curriculum has fulfilled the

major responsibilities of creating a disciplined, successful, mentally and emotionally strong and happy generation paving way for safe future and quality life.

References:

1. "Happiness curriculum Manuals" -- D.O.E.
2. "Art of Happiness" -- 14TH DALAI LAMA
3. "Jeevan Vidya" -- A. Nagraj
4. "The wisdom Bridge" - Daaji/ Kamlesh D Patel.
5. "Mindfulness" - Christophe Andre
6. "The secret to Happiness" - Mathew Sloan
7. Create Happiness Now Heartfulness - Kamlesh D Patel.

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